

Non-negative Sparse Decomposition of Musical Signal using Pre-trained Dictionary of Feature Vectors of Possible Tones from Different Instruments

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ABSTRACT

Decomposition of the musical signal into the signals of the individual instruments is a fundamental task for musical signal processing. This paper proposes a decomposition algorithm of the musical signal based on non-negative sparse estimation. We estimate the coefficients of the linear combination by assuming the feature vector of the given musical signal can be approximated as the linear combination of the elements in the pre-trained dictionary. Since the musical signal is considered as a mixture of tones from several instruments and only a few tones appear at the same time, the coefficients must be non-negative and sparse if the musical signals are represented by non-negative vectors. In this paper we used the feature vector based on the auto correlation functions. The experimental results show that the proposed decomposition method can accurately estimate the tone sequence from the musical signal played using two instruments.

1. INTRODUCTION

Decomposition of the musical signals into the signals of the individual instruments is a fundamental task for musical signal processing. This function is necessary for accurate source identification. Once the sounds of the individual instruments are accurately estimated, we can develop music search engine in which the users can search their favorite songs based on the individual instruments sounds.

Non-negative matrix Factorization (NMF) has attracted the attention of many researchers as a method to decomposing of the musical signals into the signals of individual instruments. NMF decomposes a given non-negative matrix into two non-negative matrices, respectively the dictionary matrix and the activation matrix. The dictionary matrix includes non-negative bases which characterize individual common patterns in the given data set. The activation matrix consists of non-negative coefficients which are used to approximate the non-negative input vectors represented by the given matrix by the linear combinations of the bases represented by the dictionary matrix.

We can apply NMF to various fields if the matrix is non-negative. NMF has already been applied to document anal-

ysis [1] and face analysis [2]. Also some applications of NMF to musical signal processing have been already investigated. For example, Kawamoto et al. proposed a method to estimate single sounds from chord sounds by using NMF [3].

Several extensions of NMF have been proposed to apply NMF to musical signal analysis. Kameoka et al. [4] extended the original NMF to "Complex NMF" in which the given matrix was factorized into two complex matrices. Another factorization technique is proposed by Yoshii et al. [5] that is calling Positive Semi-Definite Tensor Factorization (PSDTF). PSDTF can decompose not only non-negative spectrograms but also monaural musical signal directly into instrument sounds. It is worth mentioning that the computational complexity of the PSDTF increases as the cube of the number of the estimating parameters.

Since the musical signals usually include only a few signals of the individual instruments within the short time period, the corresponding coefficients of NMF should be sparse, namely only a few are active and all the other coefficients should be close to zero. The extension of NMF to this direction also have been investigated. P. O. Hoyer [6] introduced the concept of sparseness in NMF. This method is called non-negative sparse coding (NNSC). NNSC uses L1 regularization to make both of the coefficients and bases sparse. By this regularization, it is expected that the two non-negative matrices of NNSC become more sparse than those of the original. S. A. Abdallah et al. [7] applied NNSC to spectral basis decomposition to identify the individual spectrum from the given sequence of short-term Fourier spectra. P. Smaragdis and J. Brown [8] applied NMF with regularization for polyphonic music transcription. Tuomas Virtanen [9] extended NNSC to adopt with the temporal continuity nature of musical signal. Masahiro Nakano et al. [10] proposed nonnegative matrix factorization with markov-chained for time-varying.

NMF simultaneously decomposes a given non-negative matrix into the dictionary matrix and the activate matrix. However it is not difficult to gather the signals of each instruments in advance. It is known that human beings can distinguish the sound of instruments within a music by using prior knowledge on the signals of each instruments. If we can use such prior knowledge for the problem of the decomposition of the musical signals into the signals for the individual instruments, we can construct the dictionary of the signals of the individual instruments in advance. This means that we do not need to estimate the dictionary ma-

trix and we can simplify the algorithm.

In this paper we propose musical signal decomposition algorithm based on non-negative sparse coding using pre-trained dictionary. For simplicity we use the auto correlation function of the musical signals. It is known that auto correlation function is additive and the auto correlation function of the mixing signals are the sum of the auto correlation functions of each component signals. Since the auto coefficient function has a probability negative value, we transform the value to take only non-negative value. We call the features the non-negative normalized auto correlation vectors (nnACV). The nnACV of the music sound is used as the input of the proposed algorithm. The average of the nnACVs of the signals per instrument is used as the elements of the dictionary. The nnACV of the music sound was approximated as the linear combinations of the vectors in the dictionary. The estimated sparse non-negative coefficients of the linear combinations gives the evidence of the existence of the tone corresponding to the vector in the dictionary.

2. DICTIONARY LEARNING

At first we introduce how to make the dictionary for music decomposition. Since we can gather the sounds of the individual instruments in advance, it is easy to make the dictionary. In this paper, we use the auto correlation functions as features which characterize the sounds of each instrument. Since the normalized auto correlation functions takes the values in the range from -1 to 1 , we transform them to non-negative values.

If two signals are uncorrelated to each other, then the auto correlation function of these signals is given by the weighted sum of the auto correlation functions of the two signals, namely the linear combinations of the auto correlation functions of the two signals. Since it is possible to consider that the signals of the individual instruments are roughly independent from each other, we can decompose the auto correlation function of the mixed signals into the sum of the auto correlation functions of the individual signals by estimating the non-negative coefficients of the linear combinations.

2.1 Non-negative Normalized Auto Correlation Functions

Auto correlation is defined as the cross-correlation of a signal with itself. It computes the similarity between observations as a function of the time lag between them. It is one of the fundamental tools for signal processing.

Let $\{x(t)|t = 0, \dots, T-1\}$ be a musical signal with in a short period from $t = 0$ to $T-1$. The mean value and the variance of $x(t)$ for all times t are defined as μ_x and σ_x^2 . Then the auto correlation function $c(\tau)$ for this signal with time lag τ is given by

$$c(\tau) = \frac{E[(x(t+\tau) - \mu_x)(x(t) - \mu_x)]}{\sigma_x^2}. \quad (1)$$

Consider a mixed signal $\{z(t)|t = 0, \dots, T-1\}$ which is defined as the weighted sum of two signals $x_1(t)$ and

$x_2(t)$ as $z(t) = w_1x_1(t) + w_2x_2(t)$. The mean of value and variance of signal $z(t)$ for all times t are defined as μ_z and σ_z^2 . Then the auto correlation function of $z(t)$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned} c_z(\tau) &= \frac{E[(z(t+\tau) - \mu_z)(z(t) - \mu_z)]}{\sigma_z^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sigma_z^2} E[w_1^2x_1(t+\tau)x_1(t) \\ &\quad + w_1w_2x_1(t+\tau)x_2(t) \\ &\quad + w_2w_1x_2(t+\tau)x_1(t) \\ &\quad + w_2^2x_2(t+\tau)x_2(t)] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If the cross correlation between $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$ is 0, the auto correlation function of $z(t)$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} c_z(\tau) &\simeq \frac{1}{\sigma_z^2} E[w_1^2x_1(t+\tau)x_1(t) \\ &\quad + w_2^2x_2(t+\tau)x_2(t)] \\ &= \frac{E[w_1^2c_1(\tau) + w_2^2c_2(\tau)]}{\sigma_z^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $c_1(\tau)$ and $c_2(\tau)$ are the auto correlation functions of the signals $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$ respectively. This means that the auto correlation function of the weighted sum of two signals is approximately equal to the weighted sum of the auto correlation functions of each signal. If the cross correlation between two signals is not 0, it is impossible to estimate the weight of these two signals. Because of this, it is desirable that the two signals is independently from each other for estimating the weight these two signals from the mixed signal.

The auto correlation function takes both negative or positive values. If we normalize the auto correlation functions by $c(0)$ as

$$nc(\tau) = \frac{c(\tau)}{c(0)}, \quad (4)$$

the normalized auto correlation functions take the values in the range $[-1, 1]$. From this normalized auto correlation functions we can define the non-negative features as

$$y(\tau) = \frac{nc(\tau) + 1}{2}. \quad (5)$$

Then the non-negative normalized auto correlation features take the values in the range $[0, 1]$. We use a set of these features as the feature vector of the non-negative sparse coding which is given as $\mathbf{y} = (y(1), \dots, y(L))^T$. We call this vector non-negative normalized auto correlation vector (nnACV).

2.2 Dictionary Learning

Usually it is not difficult to gather the signals of the individual instruments. For example, it is easy to record the sounds of the target instrument. From the recorded signals of each tone of the target instruments, we calculate the nnACVs to make a dictionary for decomposing musical signals.

Consider the case where we have N different tones from several instruments and we record the sounds of each tone

M times. We denote the nnACVs calculated from the recorded sounds by $\{\mathbf{y}_i^{(j)} | i = 1, \dots, M; j = 1, \dots, N\}$, where i denotes the i -th recorded sound of the tone of the target instruments and j is the index of the tones from different instruments.

For simplicity, we use the average of the nnACVs of each tone

$$\mathbf{d}^{(j)} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \mathbf{y}_i^{(j)} \quad (6)$$

as the representative base vector of each tone. Then the dictionary matrix D is given by

$$D = \left(\mathbf{d}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{d}^{(N)} \right). \quad (7)$$

Since the dimension of the nnACV is L , the dimension of the dictionary matrix D is $L \times N$.

3. DECOMPOSITION OF MUSICAL SIGNAL

In this section we introduce how to estimate the non-negative sparse coefficients of each element in the pre-trained dictionary from a given music sound.

The music sound has melodies, harmony, and rhythm. These factors are composed as the combination of the instruments. The music sounds can be observed as a mixture of sounds from all instruments. Since we are considering to use the nnACV as the feature vector of the given music sound, the estimated coefficients must be also non-negative.

A lot of tones from different instruments appear in music, but only a few tones are played simultaneously. For examples, Piano has eighty eight keys but we use less than 10 keyboards at the same time. This means that almost all coefficients should be zero and only a few have non-zero values, namely the estimated coefficients must be sparse.

Thus we propose the decomposition method in which the non-negative sparse coefficients are estimated while the nnACV of the given music sound is approximated as the linear combinations of the vectors in the pre-trained dictionary.

3.1 Decomposition by Non-negative Sparse Coding

Let $\{x(t) | t = 0, \dots, T - 1\}$ be the musical signal recorded from the given music sound. From this signal we calculate the nnACV \mathbf{y} . We want to decompose this nnACV vector as

$$\mathbf{y} \approx \sum_{j=1}^N w_j \mathbf{d}^{(j)} = D\mathbf{w}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, \dots, w_N)^T$ is the vector of the non-negative coefficients and each element of this vector indicates the degree of the presence of the corresponding tone in the given music sound.

To evaluate the goodness of the approximation we use the squared errors between the nnACV of the musical signal and the vector estimated by the linear combination of the pre-trained dictionary. The squared errors is defined as

$$E(\mathbf{w}) = \|\mathbf{y} - D\mathbf{w}\|^2. \quad (9)$$

Data: \mathbf{y} and D

Result: \mathbf{w}

Initialize \mathbf{w}^0 to a random positive vector. Set $h = 0$;

repeat

$$\mathbf{w}^{h+1} = \mathbf{w}^h \cdot (D^T \mathbf{y} / (D^T D \mathbf{w}^h + \lambda));$$

Increment h ;

until \mathbf{w}^h converges;

Algorithm 1: Algorithm to estimate the non-negative sparse coefficients \mathbf{w} .

To make the estimated coefficients sparse, we introduce the L1 regularization and consider the cost function of the optimization as

$$Q(\mathbf{w}) = E(\mathbf{w}) + \lambda \|\mathbf{w}\|_{L1}. \quad (10)$$

Then the optimization problem for decomposition of the music sound is given as

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}} Q(\mathbf{w}) \quad \text{with constraints} \quad \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{w}, D \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

This optimization problem is similar to the one that appeared in a single column non-negative sparse coding [6]. An efficient iterative algorithm to solve this optimization is shown by P.O.Hoyer as the algorithm to estimate the activation matrix W for the non-negative sparse coding. We are only estimating the coefficients vector \mathbf{w} because the dictionary matrix D is trained in advance. On the other hand, both the basis matrix D and the activation matrix W are estimated in the original non-negative sparse coding.

The update rule to estimate the non-negative sparse coefficients vector \mathbf{w} is given as

$$\mathbf{w}^{h+1} = \mathbf{w}^h \cdot (D^T \mathbf{y} / (D^T D \mathbf{w}^h + \lambda)), \quad (12)$$

where h is the counter of the iterations. The operators \cdot and $/$ are the element-wise product and division respectively.

Thus we can summarize the algorithm to estimate the non-negative sparse coefficients vector in Algorithm 1.

4. EXPERIMENT

To confirm the effectiveness of the proposed decomposition algorithm, we have performed some experiments using the sounds generated using a MIDI sound module.

4.1 Data set

We created the music data by using MIDI sound source "KONTAKT5" released from Native Instrument. We used the sounds generated from two instruments. One is Contrabass and the other is Alto-saxophone. The sound source type of Contra-bass in "KONTAKT5" was set to "Jazz Upright" in "Upright Bass". "Band" was used as the type of Alto-saxophone. The other parameters were set to the default values. To play these sounds, MIDI sequencer "Domino" released from TAKABO Soft was used.

We connected the MIDI sequencer and the MIDI sound source by the virtual loop-back MIDI port "loopMIDI" released by Tobias Erichse. The sounds generated by the

MIDI sound source were recorded with linear pulse code modulation (LPCM) by "Audacity" and they were stored in the files with WAV format. Windows Audio Sound API (WASAPI) was used to record these sounds. The sampling-rate is set to 44100 Hz and the bit rate is 16 bits. The details of these data are shown in table1 and 2.

4.1.1 Training Data Sets for Dictionary Learning

We prepared a set of sound signals $\{s_i^{(j)} | j = 1, \dots, 24; l = 1, \dots, 3\}$ from 24 different tones from two instruments (alto-saxophone and contrabass). The sound signals were generated from 12 different notes for both alto-saxophone and contrabass. The compass of each instrument was set from C4 to B4 for alto-saxophone and from G1 to G♭2 for contrabass. To introduce the variations of the sounds, we generated the sound with 3 different values of the velocity parameter, which means the loudness parameters in MIDI (30, 60, 120). Then the value of velocity varies from 0 to 127. The length of the generated sounds in real time is about 3 seconds. We put the silent periods at the beginning and at the end for 0.5 second. So the total length of these sound signals becomes about 4 seconds. The length of each signal U was determined by the sampling rate Fs and the length of the signals in real time Ts as $U = Fs \times Ts$.

To prepare the training samples for dictionary, We cut these signals by using the rectangular window with the length T . Then the obtained signals are given as $\{x_i^{(j)} = (x_i^{(j)}(0), \dots, x_i^{(j)}(T-1))^T | i = 1, \dots, M; j = 1, \dots, 24\}$. The number of samples of each tone M was determined depending on the sampling rate Fs , the window size T , the window shift size K and the length of the original signals as $M = 3 \times (\frac{U-T-1}{K} - 1)$. Then the nnACV $y_i^{(j)}$ was calculated from each signal $x_i^{(j)}$. Finally the set of the dictionary vectors $\{d^{(j)} | j = 1, \dots, 24\}$ were obtained by using the equation 6 and the dictionary matrix D was created.

Figure 1 visualizes the dictionary matrices which are calculated from the sound signals with the sampling rates 3 kHz and 16 kHz. The first 12 columns are the feature vectors calculated from the alto-saxophone and the last 12 columns are from the contrabass.

4.1.2 Music Data for Test

We composed a jazz themed music to be used as a test sound signal which is defined as $\{s_t\}$. The tempo of the music is 120 bpm. The note value of the music is a triplet to a double half-note. Only a double note is used in contrabass part. The key of this music is C major. The chord progression is Cmaj7, A7th, Dm7 and G7th. Figure 2 shows the MIDI sequences of the alto-saxophone part and the contrabass part.

From this test signal s_t , we calculated the sequence of the non-negative normalized auto-correlation feature vectors $\{y_i | i = 1, \dots, I\}$. Here we used the same parameters (the sampling rate, auto-correlation lags, window size and window shift size) with the training samples.

(a) Dictionary created with the sampling rate 3 kHz

(b) Dictionary created with the sampling rate 16 kHz

Figure 1. Visualization of Dictionary matrix with pseudo color. These figures show that there are few differences between the two different sampling rates that we used (3 kHz, 16 kHz) under the same real time conditions.

	Alto-Saxophone	ContraBass
MIDI sound source	KONTAKT5	
MIDI sequencer	Domino	
Recording Soft	Audacity	
Sampling-rate	44100[Hz]	
pitch range	C4 - B4	G2 - G♭3
Bit	16[bits]	
Velocity	30, 60, 120	

Table 1. The basic information of the training data.

4.2 Selection of the Sampling Rate

As shown in Section 3, the approximation of the input nnACV by the linear combinations of the basis vectors in the dictionary is possible when the cross-correlations between the basis vectors become zero.

We prepared the dictionary $D = \{d^{(j)} | j = 1, \dots, 24\}$ using the sound signal with the 3 kHz and 16 kHz sampling rates. Then the cross-correlations between all possible pairs of the elements in D were calculated as

$$\rho_{kl} = \frac{d^{(k)T} d^{(l)}}{\|d^{(k)}\| \|d^{(l)}\|} \quad (k, l = 1, \dots, 24). \quad (13)$$

The figure 3 visualizes the pairwise cross-correlations $R = [\rho_{kl}]$ with pseudo colors.

From these figures, we can notice that the cross-correlations between the nnACVs calculated from the alto-saxophone are almost zero and the cross-correlations between the alto-saxophone and the contrabass are also almost zero too. While they have some values between the neighboring notes

	Alto-Saxophone	ContraBass
MIDI sound source	KONTAKT5	
MIDI sequencer	Domino	
Recording Soft	Audacity	
Sampling-rate	44100[Hz]	
pitch range	C4 - B4	G2 - G ♭ 3
Bit	16[bits]	
Velocity	61-97	50
Beat Per Minutes	120[bpm]	
Rhythm	2 beats	
The number of bars	4 bars	

Table 2. The basic information of music data.

(a) The piano roll of alto-saxophone

(b) The piano roll of contrabass

Figure 2. MIDI sequences.

of the contrabass. We also calculated the ratio of the sum of diagonal elements to the sum of all auto-correlations for two instruments by equation 14. They are summarized in the table 3.

$$Idp = \frac{\sum_i^N |\rho_{ii}|}{\sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^N |\rho_{kl}|} \leq 1. \quad (14)$$

Where Idp is the ratio of independence of dictionary. When Idp of the dictionary is 1, it is said that this dictionary is ideal independence.

From this table, the sampling rate has minor effect on the ratio of the sum of diagonal elements to all auto-correlations in the alto-saxophone. On the other hand, the sampling rate does not effect that ratio in the contrabass case at all. This difference is probably caused by the harmonic structure in high frequency area, thus higher sampling rate can capture these structure correctly and give a better score. There is no improvement for contrabass because the harmonic structure of the contrabass is in the low frequency

	3[kHz], $L = 300$	16[kHz], $L = 1600$
Alto-sax	0.6717	0.7619
Contrabass	0.2363	0.2304
Mixed	0.2901	0.3235

Table 3. The ratio of the sum of diagonal elements to the total sum of all cross-correlations.

(a) Calculated using the vectors in the dictionary with the sampling rate 3 kHz

(b) Calculated using the vectors in the dictionary with the sampling rate 16 kHz

Figure 3. Visualization of the pairwise cross-correlations between the vectors in the learned dictionary.

area only.

We use 3 kHz down sampled signals for the following experiments because the differences with the sampling rates are not so large.

4.3 Decomposition of Music Sound

To confirm the effectiveness of the proposed decomposition algorithm, we applied the proposed non-negative sparse decomposition algorithm to the prepared music sound. We performed the decomposition experiments with three different lengths ($T = 600, 900, 1200$). If T is set to a small value, the window size becomes short and we can get more samples from the prepared music sound. We got 1133, 1123, and 903 samples from the cases of $T = 600$, $T = 900$, and $T = 1200$ respectively.

The sparseness parameter λ was changed from 0 to 400 with an incremental step size of 10. If the number of iterations of the proposed decomposition algorithm exceeds 500 times without convergence, the algorithm stops.

Figure 4 shows some results of the decomposition by the proposed algorithm. The alto-saxophone part is shown in the upper half of each figure and the contrabass part is shown in the lower half. The x-axis is the sequence number of the extracted signals marked by the rectangle window. For each extracted signal, we applied the proposed algorithm and then the coefficients of the vectors in the pre-trained dictionary were estimated. The values of the estimated coefficients are shown in the row as pseudo color. Since the dictionary was constructed by using the sounds of each note from each instruments, the sequence of the estimated coefficients shown in Figure 4 should be the same

(a) $L = 600, \lambda = 150$

(b) $L = 900, \lambda = 220$

(c) $L = 1200, \lambda = 270$

Figure 4. Decomposition results of the test music. These figures visualize the coefficients of the dictionary components with pseudo color. The alto-saxophone part is shown in the upper half of each figure and the contrabass part is shown in the lower half. The red color means the value of coefficient marks high, on the other hand, the blue color means that marks low.

as the MIDI sequence. This means that the coefficients from the first row to the 12th row are represented as $B4, B\flat4, \dots, C4$ in alto-saxophone and from 13th to 24th row are represented as $G\flat3, F3, \dots, G2$ in contrabass.

From these results we can say that the proposed decomposition algorithm can decompose the music sound played with two instruments into the notes of each instrument almost correctly. Since the cross-correlations between the vectors of alto-saxophone in the dictionary are almost zero, the accuracy of the alto-saxophone part is better while some mistakes have occurred at the contrabass part.

To improve the accuracy, we have to develop an algorithm to construct the uncorrelated vectors in the dictionary.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a musical signal decomposition algorithm based on non-negative sparse coding using pre-trained dictionary. For simplicity we used the non-negative normalized auto correlation vector (nnACV) of the musical signals as the input of the proposed algorithm. The average values of the nnACVs of the signals of the individual instruments were used as elements of the dictionary. The nnACV of the music sound was approximated as the linear combinations of the vectors in the dictionary. The estimated sparse non-negative coefficients of the linear combinations give the evidence of the existence of the tone corresponding to the vector in the dictionary. We confirmed that the proposed algorithm could appropriately decompose the music sound generated using two instruments through the experiments.

Since the auto-correlation vectors in the dictionary are highly dimensional and the cross-correlations between them

are not completely uncorrelated, it is necessary to develop an algorithm to construct uncorrelated dictionary with reduced dimension. This is one of our future works.

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